

Probability and Relative Derivative $d/dy \ln(P)$

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For the case of physical quantities with units, such as mass, time, length etc, a change in the value of the quantity makes sense by itself in addition to a relative change. In other words, one does not need to know the mass of an object to understand what a change of 1 kg is. Probability, on the other hand, is a strictly relative quantity and so needs to be normalized. If it is not normalized, one needs to know relative probabilities. To say that an unnormalized probability changes by a value of 10 does not mean anything. Given that equations often solve for an unnormalized probability function, we argue that the notion of the relative probability should appear in equations. Even in the case of $\ln(P(y))$, called information in information theory, for which there is no derivative, taking a derivative, say d/dy , immediately creates a relative probability derivative. Thus the form $\ln(P)$ is in keeping with the notion of a relative derivative.

Here we examine the idea of a relative derivative and its association with information $\ln(P)$, Fisher information, quantum mechanics and the Fokker-Planck equation as well as classical statistical balance in the presence of a potential.

Quantities with units versus Probability

If a quantity has units, we argue that this constitutes a relative measurement. For example, a given length must be compared to a ruler in order to find its value. Thus its value exists relative to the ruler gradations. If one is familiar with the ruler gradations, then it makes sense to say that a length increases by say 10 m.

In the case of probability, there is no unit and no external measure which may be used for comparison. Rather there is an internal comparison based on the options available and their weights. This is why one either uses normalized probability values (so that a change of .1 means a 10% change) or compares various nonnormalized weights i.e. makes internal relative measurements.

Theories with corresponding equations exist to allow one to derive the mathematical form of probability distributions, but these usually focus on the unnormalized function. Given this function, one may immediately create the normalization factor by summing/integrating. These equations often contain derivatives of the probability, but we argue that such a derivative only makes sense relative to the unnormalized probability. Thus we expect to see the notion of a relative probability derivative appear in theories/equations used to determine probabilities. We examine a number of these.

Information $\ln(P)$ and Shannon's Entropy

Shannon's entropy - Sum over i $P(e_i/T) \ln(P(e_i/T))$ may be maximized (d/dP) subject to a constraint, such as average energy, to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. In such a case one has: $\ln(e_i/T) = -e_i/T$ and a relative probability derivative does not appear. If one, however, takes the derivative with respect to d/dy where $y=e_i/T$, then a relative derivative

emerges. Thus the form $\ln(P)$ is linked with a relative derivative, we argue. This becomes more apparent when one examines another statistical form, namely Fisher information.

Fisher Information

Fisher's information: $\int dx P(x) \{d \ln P(x) / dx\}^2$ ((1)) demonstrates the presence of a relative probability derivative. This quantity is used in statistical mechanics, but according to the principle of extreme physical information, it may be extremized subject to an appropriate constraint to obtain various physical equations, including, it is argued in the literature (1), the Schrodinger equation. Thus the idea of a relative probability distribution is central to many physical equations, not just in physics, which are linked to Fisher information extremization.

Quantum Mechanics

We argue that quantum mechanics is based on free particle quantum behaviour, namely the wavefunction $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ which we argue is a kind of probability (two dimensional). $\exp(ipx)$ (unnormalized) is an eigenfunction of the translational operator (times $-i$) i.e.

$$-i d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \rightarrow -i d/dx \ln(\exp(ipx)) = p \quad ((2))$$

Again one sees the idea of information and the relative probability derivative. This carries over into a single particle bound state when one utilizes an ensemble of $\exp(ipx)$'s with the normalization $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) = \text{wavefunction}$. Thus average momentum is:

$$-i dW/dx / W = -i d/dx \ln(W) \quad ((3))$$

Average kinetic energy also involves the normalization W i.e. $KE_{ave} = \{-1/2m d/dx dW/dx\} / W$. ((4))

Given that $W(x)$ represents a kind of square root probability, one again considers a quantity relative to this probability.

Pressure Balance in Classical Statistical Mechanics

Given a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas in a potential $V(x)$, instead of using microscopic considerations, one may use the ideal gas law $\text{Pressure} = \text{density}(x) RT$ (which may be obtained experimentally or from microscopic calculations) and balance it with Newtonian force $F(x)$ multiplied by $\text{density}(x)$ in a little box i.e.

$$\text{Pressure}(x+dx)dA - \text{Pressure}(x)dA = F(x) \text{density}(x) dA dx \quad \text{or}$$

$$RT d \text{density}(x) / dx = F(x) \text{density} = -dV/dx \text{density} \quad ((4a))$$

$$\text{Or density} = C \exp(-V(x) / T) \quad ((4b))$$

((4a)) is in the form of $d/dx \ln(\text{density}(x))$ so the relative probability derivative appears.

Fokker-Planck Equation

Finally we consider the case of the Fokker-Planck equation (2) for a drift coefficient $= p$ *constant, where p is momentum i.e.

$$dP/dt \text{ partial} = -d/dp \{ p \text{ constant } P \} + d/dp d/dp \{ D(p,t)P(e) \} \text{ where } e=pp/2m \quad ((5))$$

d/dp is the partial derivative with respect to p .

$$\text{For } dP/dt \text{ partial} = 0: \quad -p C1 P + d/dp (DP) = C1 P + d/de (DP) 1/m = 0 \rightarrow$$

$$dP/de / P = m (C1 - 1/m dD/de) / D \quad ((6))$$

Thus $d\ln(P)/de$ appears on the LHS of ((6)) and one again has a relative probability derivative.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a change in unnormalized probability does not carry meaning by itself because there is no measure with which to compare this quantity. We argue that one should consider a relative probability derivative i.e. $dP/de / P = d\ln(P)/de$. There exist various theories/equations which are used to derive unnormalized probability expressions. We suggest these should be in the form of or associated with the relative probability derivative i.e. $d\ln(P)/de$. We show that information, Shannon's entropy, Fisher's information, quantum mechanics, classical statistical mechanical pressure balance and the Fokker-Planck equation for a drift coefficient $= p$ * constant (p =momentum) all use the notion of relative probability derivative.

References

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